

Paper Electrophoretic Studies on Metal Complexes of Methycysteine

BRIJ BHUSHAN TEWARI

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, Roorkee-247 667

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The use of paper electrophoresis for the study of metal complex systems seems to be well established¹. A search of literature indicated that there is no report on Cu^{II} and Co^{II} binary complexes with methycysteine. The complexation data involving essential metal ions and biactive sulphur containing ligand methycysteine gives insight into many physiochemical processes. The present paper reports the study of interaction of Cu^{II} and Co^{II} with methycysteine.

Results and Discussion

The plot of overall electrophoretic speed of metal spot against pH gives a curve with a number of plateaus (Fig. 1). A constant speed over a range of pH is possible only when a particular complex species is overwhelmingly

Fig. 1. Mobility curves for the metal-methycysteine systems : (O) Cu^{II}-methycysteine and (●) Co^{II}-methycysteine; temp. = 35°, ionic strength = 0.1 M.

formed. Thus, every plateau is indicative of formation of a certain complex species. The first one in the beginning corresponds to a region in which metal ions are uncomplexed. This region of low pH, concentration of [H₂C(SCH₃)-CH(NH₃⁺)COOH] species of methycysteine is maximum and this species is non-complexing. Beyond this range, metal ion spots have progressively decreasing mobility, complexation of metal ions should be taking place with anionic species of methycysteine whose concentration in-

creases progressively with the increase of pH. Fig. 1 shows three plateaus in both Cu^{II} and Co^{II}. Hence both Cu^{II} and Co^{II} form two complexes with methycysteine anion. The literature also assigns prominent liganding property to the zwitterion species². It is therefore assumed that anionic species [H₂C(SCH₃)CH(NH₂)COO⁻] of methycysteine has complexed with the metal ions to form different complexes with the metal ions.

Fig. 1 reveals that Cu^{II} and Co^{II} metal ions form their first complex movements towards negative electrode. Hence one [H₂C(SCH₃)CH(NH₂)COO⁻] must have combined with Cu^{II} and Co^{II} metal ion to give [Cu{H₂C(SCH₃)-CH(NH₂)COO}]⁺ and [Co{H₂C(SCH₃)CH(NH₂)COO}]⁺ complex cation respectively. With further increase of pH, mobility in both the metal ions decreases giving rise to third plateau with zero indicates its neutral nature. The third plateau in each case is due to (1 : 2) metal-ligand complex. Hence, two [H₂C(SCH₃)CH(NH₂)COO⁻] must have combined with Cu^{II} and Co^{II} to give [Cu{H₂C(SCH₃)-CH(NH₂)COO}]₂ and [Co{H₂C(SCH₃)CH(NH₂)COO}]₂ metal complexes. In view of the above observation, the complexation of metal ions with methycysteine anion may be represented as

where, M²⁺ = Cu²⁺ and Co²⁺ metal cation; [L⁻] = methycysteine anion; K₁, K₂ are first and second stability constants respectively.

The two regions of decreasing mobility represent conditions where two forms co-exist. The overall mobility is given by well-known equation³,

$$U = \frac{u_0 + u_1 K_1 [L^{-}] + u_2 K_1 K_2 [L^{-}]^2}{1 + K_1 [L^{-}] + K_1 K_2 [L^{-}]^2} \quad (3)$$

where, u₀, u₁ and u₂ are mobility of uncomplexed, 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal complexes.

Concentration of methycysteine anion [L⁻] at pH of interest is calculated by using analytical concentration and pK values of pure methycysteine (pK₁ = 2.55, pK₂ = 8.55). The concentration of chelating methycysteine anion [L⁻] is calculated from equation,

$$[L^-] = \frac{[L_T]}{1 + [H]/K_2 + [H]^2/K_1K_2} \quad (4)$$

where, $[L_T]$ is the total concentration. For calculating first stability constant (K_1) the region between first and second plateau is pertinent. The first stability constant, (K_1) = $1/[L^-]$. The second stability constant (K_2) of the second complex can be calculated by taking into consideration the region between second and third plateau of mobility curve. These calculated values are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY COMPLEXES OF Cu^{II} AND Co^{II} *

Ionic strength = 0.1 mol dm^{-3} , temp. = $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$,
Methylcysteine anion $[L^-] = [\text{H}_2\text{C}(\text{SCH}_3)\text{CH}(\text{NH}_2)\text{COO}^-]$

Metal ions	First complex	$\log K_{1\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$	Second complex	$\log K_{2\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$
Calculated values :				
Cu^{II}	$[\text{CuL}]^+$	5.35 ± 0.08	$[\text{CuL}_2]$	4.75 ± 0.12
Co^{II}	$[\text{CoL}]^+$	4.25 ± 0.05	$[\text{CoL}_2]$	3.55 ± 0.10
Literature values :				
Cu^{II}	$[\text{CuL}]^+$	7.88^a	$[\text{CuL}_2]$	6.84^a
		7.88^b		6.84^b
Co^{II}	$[\text{CoL}]^+$	4.12^a	$[\text{CoL}_2]$	4.12^a
		3.49^b		3.49^b

$K_{1\text{ML}}^{\text{M}} = [\text{ML}]/[\text{M}][\text{L}]$; $\log K_{2\text{ML}}^{\text{M}} = [\text{ML}_2]/[\text{ML}][\text{L}]$; $[L^-]$ = ligand (methylcysteine).

^aRef. 6. ^bRef. 7.

It is observed (Table 1) that values of first and second stability constants of Cu^{II} -methylcysteine complex are greater than those of Co^{II} -methylcysteine complex. So, it is inferred that bond formed between Cu^{II} and methylcysteine anion is stronger in comparison to Co^{II} -methylcysteine bond. The order of stability of metal complexes tally with those reported in the literature⁴.

The divergence in the values obtained from different sources is mainly due to the difference in temperature and ionic strength used by different workers. Nevertheless in view of the uncertainty (5%) attending to the measurement of the mobility of the metal spots, the results reported here are fairly reliable.

It may be concluded that Cu^{II} and Co^{II} are essential for biological systems, but as such they are toxic, and methylcysteine may be used to reduce the levels of these metal ions in living cells.

Experimental

The apparatus and procedure were as described earlier¹. Metal perchlorates were prepared by the precipitation of metal carbonates from their nitrates with sodium carbonate, which were washed with boiling water and treated with calculated amounts of 1% perchloric acid. These were heated and filtered. The metal contents of the filtrates were determined and final concentrations were kept at $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$.

A 0.1% (w/v) solution of 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN) in ethanol was used for detecting the metal ions. A saturated solution of silver nitrate in acetone was sprayed on the paper and subsequently fumed with NH_3 to detect glucose in the spot. All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Stock solutions of 2.0 M perchloric acid, 2.0 M NaOH and 0.1 M methylcysteine were prepared from AnalaR samples. Each solution was standardised as usual. The background electrolyte consisted of a mixture containing 0.1 M perchloric acid and $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ methylcysteine.

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